

APPLICATION OF SPIRAL PRINCIPLES OF LIVING NATURE IN FURNITURE

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Annotation: This article discusses different types of spirals. Similar spirals are considered, which are close, but not exactly the same as the golden spiral, with which they are often confused. Changes in the shape of natural structures in the form of a spiral and how they affect the design of furniture. Examples of various types of spirals in nature and furniture are given.

Keywords: spiral, hyperbolic spiral, Fibonacci spiral, Archimedes' spiral, Fermat's spiral, Rod spiral, hyperbolic spiral

Bionics is a branch of science whose efforts are aimed at the study of biological systems and processes occurring in wildlife, and at their creative use in design objects.

Nature often inspires designers to create unusual yet functional interior items. Some people are led to new ideas by a tree leaf or the way insects move, but you can bypass this level and immediately turn to the origins of the development and functioning of living organisms.

A spiral is one of the forms of manifestation of movement, growth and development of life. Describing a spiral, the stems of plants are stretched, moving in a spiral, the petals of some flowers, for example, phloxes, open, fern shoots unfold. Changing the shape of a natural structure in the form of a spiral leads to stability in space and the appearance of additional rigidity in the structure.

Depending on the direction of movement, the spiral shapes have left and right orientations. Spiral formations have a different configuration in the form of a geometric spiral or a helical curve. A geometric spiral is a curve that is described by a point moving at a constant speed of acceleration or deceleration

along a ray that rotates around a fixed point of the pole at a constant angular speed. A screw is a special case of a spiral. Both the screw and the helix belong to the helical symmetry, as they have a helical axis of symmetry.

The logarithmic spiral is the only type of spiral that does not change its shape with increasing size. This property explains why the logarithmic spiral is so common in nature.

The peculiarity of a logarithmic spiral, which has an infinite number of turns, is that the distance between its turns (or, in other words, the size of the turns) depends on the distance between them and the center - the pole - of the spiral: with an increase in this distance, and increases exponentially distance between coils. It should be noted that, despite the change in the size of the turns, their shape never changes.

Most natural forms have a logarithmic spiral configuration. The animal kingdom provides us with examples of spirals of shells, snails, and molluscs. All these forms point to a natural phenomenon: the winding process is associated with the growth process. In fact, a snail shell is nothing more, nothing less than a cone wrapped around itself.

If we look closely at the growth of shells and horns, we notice another curious property: growth occurs only at one end. And this property preserves a shape completely unique among curves in mathematics, the shape of a logarithmic, or equiangular spiral.

The Fibonacci spiral is a pattern of creativity and regeneration for the purpose of connecting energy. This is geometrically described in the construction of a logarithmic spiral, or a spiral that grows exponentially. The connected circles that create the golden spiral can demonstrate this fact in form.

The golden spiral appears when geometrically growing circles connect at the intersection points. This particular construction is based on the Fibonacci sequence. This model is a pattern of growth, which is also a form at the same time. Germinating seeds and embryos are a striking example in nature.

Archimedes' spiral is a spiral described by a point moving along a rotating circle. The geometric property that characterizes the Archimedes spiral is the constancy of the distances between adjacent turns.

Fermat's spiral (sometimes a parabolic spiral) - a spiral defined on a plane in polar coordinates, is a type of Archimedean spiral. Scientist Vogel in 1979 proposed a model for the distribution of flowers and seeds in sunflowers. This is the shape of Fermat's spiral. A pineapple has eight spirals to the right and thirteen to the left. A pine cone has five spirals twisted to the right and eight twisted to the left. In a sunflower, 34 and 55, respectively.

Spiral "Wand", lituus - a flat transcendental curve. The curve tends from infinity to the point (0; 0), twisting around it in a counterclockwise spiral. The "Wand" spiral is a special case of the Archimedean spiral. The curve was described by Roger Coates in a collection called Harmonic Measurements (1722). Kots called it lituus because of its resemblance to the wand of the ancient Roman augurs. This curve has an inflection point.

A hyperbolic spiral is a plane transcendental curve. The equation of a hyperbolic spiral in a polar coordinate system is the inverse of the equation of the Archimedean spiral.

The Cornu spiral is a flat transcendental spiral curve. The curve has two branches symmetrically located relative to the origin. The curve is named after the French physicist Konyu, who used it to study the diffraction of light. The Cornu spiral is also called the clothoid, as well as the Etzler spiral.

Cylindrical helix. Such a line in space is described by a point that moves along any generatrix of a right circular cylinder rotating around its axis so that the path traveled by the point along the generatrix is proportional to the angle of rotation of the cylinder. Cylindrical spirals are spatial curves that extend on the surface of the cylinder and cut at a right angle one of the sides of the rectangle formed on the surface of the cylinder. Helix is a curve that ordinary ivy draws when wrapping around a tree.

Conical helix. Such a line is described by a point that moves along any generatrix of a right circular cone rotating around its axis so that the path traveled by the point along the generatrix is always equal to the angle of rotation of the cone.

Horizontal projections of a conical helix is the Archimedes spiral - one of the wonderful flat curved lines.

List of sources used:

1. Benyus J. Biomimicry: Innovation inspired by nature. - New York: HarperCollins Publishers Inc., 2002. — 309 с.

2. Биотехнология: учебник / А. Я. Самуйленко [и др.]; под ред. А. Я. Самуйленко. – 2-е перераб. изд. – М, 2013. – 746 с.

3. Биотехнология. Научные основы инженерного оформления биотехнологий: учеб. пособие / Саратов. гос. аграр. ун-т им. Н. И. Вавилова. – Саратов: КУБик, 2014

4. Воронцова З. Мастерская природы. .— М.: Изобразительное искусство, 1981

5. Clark Graeme M. Sounds from Silence: Graeme Clark and the Bionic Ear Story. - Allen & Unwin, 2003. — 247 p.

6. Газит, Э. Нанобиотехнология: необъятные перспективы развития / Э. Газит ; пер. с англ. А. Е. Соловченко ; науч. ред. Н. Л. Клячко. – Москва : Науч. мир, 2011– 149 с.

7. J. Rakhmanov APPLICATION OF DIFFERENT POPULAR STYLES IN FURNITURE DESIGN // SAI. 2023. №А1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/application-of-different-popular-styles-in-furniture-design> (дата обращения: 23.02.2023)

8. Рахманов, Жажонгир Мамашарибович. "ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ БИОНИЧЕСКОГО МЕТОДА В ДИЗАЙНЕ МЕБЕЛИ." *Conferencea* (2022): 58-61.

9. Rakhmanov J.M. HISTORY OF THE FURNITURE INDUSTRY. ARTISTIC IMAGE IN DESIGN. Science and Education in Karakalpakstan. 2022 №3/2 ISSN 2181-9203

10. Mamasharibovich R. J. Zamonaviy Mebel Dizayn Turlari Va Ularning Tasniflanishi //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 22-28.

11. Абдусалямова Ш. К. Дизайн плиты и вытяжки для современного интерьера //Наука, образование и культура. – 2020. – №. 5 (49). – С. 67-69.

12. Одилова С. Д. История создания предметов мебели у народов среднеазиатского региона //Проблемы науки. – 2020. – №. 6 (54).

13. Дмитриева И.В. Бионические закономерности в строительной технике.//Эпоха науки. 2021. №28 URL: http://eraofscience.com/index/28_december_2021/0-144

14. Дмитриева И.В. Роль цветовых гармоний в архитектурном декоре Центральной Азии // Наука, образование и культура. 2020 №5 (49).URL: <http://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rol-tsvetovyh-garmoniy-v-arhitekturnom-dekore-tsentralnoy-azii>

15. Абдусалямова Ш.К. Дизайн плиты и вытяжки для современного интерьера //Наука, образование и культура. – 2020. – №. 5 (49). – С. 67-69.

16. Odilova S.D. Gold cut in every view //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 1989-1991.

17. AxmedjanovaU.B. Features Of The Profession Of A Designer// Science and Education in Karakalpakstan. – 2023. – №. 1/1 (30). – С. 39-42.

18. Ma'rufov F.O. Some types of transformation used in sofas //Science and innovation. International scientific journal volume 2 issue 2 february 2023. ISSN: 2181-3337.

19. Ахмеджанова У.Б. "ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ КОНТРАСТА ДОПОЛНИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЦВЕТОВ В ДИЗАЙНЕ" "ILM – FAN TA`LIMDA INNOVATSION

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OMMABOP KONFERENSIYASI 2022, № 17, 1595-1960 bet**